

Recruitment Messages

a) For Public Channels

Hello [Channel Name] community,

We are a team of researchers from [University Name], and our current study aims to uncover gaps in the advice ecosystem and assess the awareness levels among Indian UPI users regarding privacy and security issues.

We would love to invite someone from the community to participate in an interview and share their insights on this topic.

You can email me directly at [Email ID] if you have any questions or want to schedule an interview.

Thanks for your time,
[Researcher Name]

b) For Private Emails

Dear [Name],

We are a group of researchers from [University Name] and our research is about understanding how UPI users observe and navigate the privacy and security aspects of their transactions. We believe that your insights could help us understand many details. If you would be willing to share your thoughts and experiences through an interview, we would greatly appreciate it.

If you prefer not to participate, please accept our apologies, and you can simply disregard this email.

Thank you for considering our invitation, and we look forward to your response.

Best Regards,
[Researcher Name]

c) For Private Texts

Dear [Name],

We are a research team from [University Name] conducting interviews focusing on the study of UPI privacy and security.

Your insights are very much appreciated and thank you for taking the time to consider this,
[Researcher Name]

d) For Private Phone Calls

Hello, this is [Researcher Name] from [University Name]. I hope you're doing well. We're a research team conducting interviews focusing on UPI privacy and security issues. Your insights can truly make a significant impact on our research.

Thank you for taking the time to consider this and looking forward to your response. Have a great day!